

KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS (KPIs), HR SCORE, AND THE BALANCED SCORECARD

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Abstract: This article aims to provide an overview of strategic management aspects for an organization. The manner varied resources are arranged and utilized and the manner they are put in motion through a balanced scorecard. A systematic overview of key performance indicators, HR score, and a balanced scorecard has been presented. The article would provide an insight to those who prepare to develop a scorecard. Despite the fact that there would be no any final or ultimate scorecard however, still it would require certain logics in developing appropriate questionnaire with variables and co variables. Things have changed continuously since Kaplan and Norton introduced the balanced scorecard.

Key words: *Performance Management; Key Performance Indicators (KPIs); HR Score; Balanced Score Card*

INTRODUCTION

Doing a business amidst increasing competition and a changing marketplace would be never an easy job. Corporates can come up and vanish even without making any mark or even may not be sustained for a long. Therefore, restructures, transformations, mergers, acquisitions, disposals and offshoring have become an order of the day as well as night in the business ecosystem. HR experts have developed many methods and techniques to evaluate the performance however, none could be termed as a final. Ultimately, there is all the possibility that a better version would emerge every time mind would be applied.

SOME FAMOUS QUOTES

In the words of *Lawrence Whitman* “A direct link between human capital and corporate financial results is not readily apparent in traditional accounting practices. Right now, we are only beginning to understand the potential for this tool, but it’s the measurement process that’s important. Once we are able to measure intangible assets more accurately, I think investors and finance professionals will begin to look at human capital metrics as another indicator of a company’s value.”

Robert Kaplan and *David Norton* “When it comes to specific measures concerning HR and people-related issues, companies have devoted virtually no effort to measure either outcome or the drivers of these capabilities. This gap is disappointing, since one of the most important goals for adopting the scorecard measurement and management framework is to promote the growth of individual and organizational capabilities. This reflects the limited progress that most organizations have made linking employees and organizational alignment with their strategic objectives.”

Brian Becker, *Mark Huselid* and *Dave Ulrich* stated that “Clearly, designing any new measurement system for

intangible assets isn’t easy – if it were, most companies would have already done it. Embracing this challenge takes time and a lot of careful thought. Real innovation comes only when people work together on the most pressing challenges of the workplace.”

“While much of the work of an HR scorecard is technical, the delivery of the scorecard is personal. It requires that HR professionals desire to make a difference, align their work to business strategy, apply the science of research to the art of HR and commit to learning from constant experimentation. When you create the HR scorecard, using the approach we describe, you are actually linking HR to firm performance. But you will also develop a new perspective of your HR function, practices and professional development. In measurement terms, the benefits will far outweigh the costs.”

Sears in the early 1990s suggested that ideas and innovations should be supported and the workplace should be made tension free. *Sears* developed a series of competencies and behavioral objectives designed to reach each goal. These competencies became the foundation on which to build recruiting, training, and compensation and performance structures. *Sears* developed that managers could say with confidence that a 5 point improvement in employee attitude drove a 1.3 point improvement in customer satisfaction, which in turn drove a.5 percent improvement in revenue growth.

WHAT IS EXPECTED DELIVERABLES OF HR?

Human resources are no more an overhead, it can become a valuable strategic partner that can help the company achieve its goals. Therefore, it is required to identify and measure the HR deliverables that support corporate strategy and the HR systems that create those deliverables.

Recruiting, training, performance and compensation structures based upon a reward structure can recognize employee’s ideas and innovations. For creating a high performance work system we must focus on HR professionals

with strategic competencies. In a *High-Performance Work System* (HPWS), each element of the HR system is designed to maximize the overall quality of human capital throughout the organization. HPWS links the selection and promotion decisions to validated competency models; as well as it develops strategies that provide timely and effective support for the skills demanded by the firm's strategy. Moreover, it enacts compensation and performance management policies that attract, retain and motivate high-performance employees.

Most HR departments don't measure HR contributions to company success. It required developing an innovative assessment system that measures HR's contribution to what matters the most, the firm profitability and shareholder value. Therefore, prior to moving an HR scorecard it has been suggested to ensure certain steps.

HUMAN RESOURCES KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS (KPSS)

The first step of implementing an HR scorecard would be the continuous monitoring and reporting of the defined targets i.e. strategic goals which are achieved. *KPIs* in this regard would serve as a major phase of implementation of an HR scorecard. *Key performance indicators (KPIs)* are mirrors of the organizational performance. Management in the entrepreneurial sector nowadays usually have many KPIs to choose but all of chosen KPIs must be connected to the HR mission. KPIs have to be linked to all partial goals within the strategy map therefore, it would be essential to assign the required strategic value which will have expressing power about the level of organization performance. KPIs can be arranged in terms of *lagging* and *leading*. Recruiting costs, qualification index, posts filled by internal sources or leadership index can be put into leading one because the results of these indicators can influence the HRM for the future. *Lagging indicator* is a metric that mainly refers to past developments and effects/results, e.g. reflects history and outcomes of certain actions and processes.

In general, implementation of HR scorecard has the same rules and steps among organizations in a frame of the entrepreneurial environment e. g. in business companies or in financial houses. The main aim of all organizations should be to have a manageable and sustainable HR scorecard with visible and measurable KPIs. Many companies used to use different tools for measuring their performance in order to stay in business and come in contact with tough competition. Such reasons compel an organization to measure performance of the organization and contribute to the stability of the organization in today's competitive environment. Some organizations try to measure performance, according to the financial drivers, but in the recent period top leaders attempted to find new performance indicators to remain ahead in the market.

Key performance indicators can be assigned to each perspective in strategy map and KPIs on HR level can become significant benchmark. KPIs are valid and effective when applied in a consistent and comprehensive manner. Further, the financial performance must be respected as the critical measure of the success for every business but financial KPIs should be a closely related set of operational metrics. Once KPIs are identified, defined and formalized yet it is not all over because it must be based upon a valid and non-manipulated data. Organizations should identify areas of

business processes that are the most critical to the financial success of the organization.

Eckerson (2007) described good KPIs as having the following features:-

Sparse: The fewer KPIs the better.

Drillable: Users can drill into detail.

Simple: Users understand the KPI.

Actionable: Users know how to affect outcomes.

Owned: KPIs has an owner.

Referenced: Users can view origins and context.

Correlated: KPIs drive desired outcomes.

Balanced: KPIs consist of both financial and non-financial metrics.

Aligned: KPIs doesn't undermine each other.

Validated: Workers can't circumvent the KPIs.

On the other hand, Hursman (2010) defined *SMART* as next five criteria for effective KPIs:

Specific

Measurable

Attainable

Relevant

Time bound

The setting of appropriate KPIs on HR level is not so easy and sometimes it can take longer as the management presents. Top leaders should take into account all organizational aspects it means financial situation, market position and also the vision of the company. The base for setting proper KPIs is formulating the strategy map and understanding the consequences between human resources management and significant company's targets. Further next fundamental step for applicable KPIs is relevant partial goal in Learning and Growth perspective. Creation of the partial targets can be time consuming, but it is necessary to pay attention to it. Consequent evaluation of the results has its importance due to the application of possible changes during the implementation and thus it makes the organization more competitive and flexible. Essential process of the implementation i.e. sustaining the positive development of HR strategy is the continual performed of the HR activities and HR action plan and measures e.g. Arisen out of the employee survey. In the beginning, the company doesn't have to define many HR activities. The key of the HR success is not to underestimate it. (Iveta, 2012)

In a nutshell, it can be concluded that the organizations needed to give priority for organizations to use KPIs in a business context at all times, to measure customer and service margins, make effective business decisions and offer exciting customer propositions to drive business forward.

WHAT IS AN HR SCORE?

The most potent action HR managers can take to ensure their strategic contribution is to develop a measurement system that convincingly showcases HR's impact on business performance. That system is the HR Scorecard. (Brian E. Becker, 2001). The HR (human resources) scorecard matches business strategy against HR deliverables and objectives to provide a statistical basis by which HR efficiency and contribution to strategy implementation can be measured. (Brian Becker, 2001)

An HR scorecard is a management tool which allows a business to:

1. Manage HR as a strategic asset and a source of competitive advantage.
2. Quantitatively demonstrate HR's contribution to the firm's financial results and bottom-line profitability.
3. Create and measure the degree of alignment between the strategy of the business and its HR architecture.

When used effectively, HR scorecards link the things people do with the strategy of the company. The HR scorecard also allows an HR architecture to evolve which is measurement managed and systematic. And the HR scorecard allows the human resource function to fill a strategic role in the business – participating fully in the balanced goals of cutting costs and creating added value.

In total, the HR scorecard makes it possible for HR to enhance its role as a strategic business asset.

Ulrich et al. discussed a seven step model for formalizing the strategic role of HR. They are:

1. Defining Business Strategy:

HR managers should focus on implementation of strategy. By doing so, they can facilitate discussion about how to communicate the firm's goals throughout the organization. Goals should be clear otherwise, these vague goals will tend to confuse employees and they would not know how exactly to implement the strategies.

2. Building a case for HR as a strategic asset:

Once a firm clarifies its strategy, HR professionals need to build a clear case for the strategic role of HR. They must be able to explain how and why HR can support the strategy. It is important to look at as much of case histories and internal as well as external research while going through this phase.

3. Creating a Strategy Map:

This paves the way for the implementation process. But, before this is done, the firm must get a clear understanding of its value chain. The value chain is the complex cumulative set of interactions and combinatorial effects that create the customer value in the products and services of the firm. It is important that the firm's performance management system must account for each of the links and dependencies in the value chain.

4. Identifying HR deliverables within the strategy map:

HR creates much of its value of the points of intersection between the HR system and the overall strategy implementation system of the organization. Thus, to leverage this to the maximum possible extent it is important that there is a clear understanding of both sides of this intersection.

5. Aligning the HR architecture with the HR deliverables:

It is also important to consider how the HR system made up of the rewards, competencies; work organization etc. needs to be structured to provide the deliverables that are identified in the strategy map.

6. Designing the Strategic HR measurement system:

The next step is to design the measurement system itself. This requires a new, modern perspective on measuring HR performance. It also requires HR to resolve several new technical issues that it might not be familiar with. To accurately measure the HR-firm performance relationship, it is imperative that the firm develops valid measures of HR deliverables. This task has two dimensions. Firstly, HR has to be confident that they have chosen the correct HR deliverables. This requires that HR has a clear understanding of the causality in the value chain for effective strategy implementation. Secondly, HR must choose the correct

measures for those deliverables. During this process of developing the HR scorecard, the firm might go through several stages of increasing sophistication.

7. Implementing the strategy by using the measures:

This step is to use this powerful new management tool in the right way. This tool not only helps the firm measure HR's impact on firm performance, but also helps HR professionals have new insights into what steps must be taken to maintain HR as a strategic asset. It helps the HR professionals dig deeper into the causes of success and failure and helps them promote the former and avoid the latter.

BENEFITS OF THE HR SCORECARD

An HR scorecard reinforces the distinction between HR doable and deliverables. The HR measurement system must clearly distinguish between the deliverables that influence strategy implementation and doable that do not. Policy implementation is not a deliverable until it has a positive effect on the HR architecture and creates the right employee behaviors that drive strategy implementation. An appropriate HR measurement system will encourage HR professionals to think both strategically as well as operationally. It enables cost control and value creation: HR is always expected to control costs for the firm. At the same time, HR has to fulfill its strategic goal, which is to create value. The HR scorecard helps HR professionals balance the two and find the optimal solution. It allows HR professionals to drive out costs where appropriate, but at the same time defends investments in intangibles and HR by outlining the benefits in concrete terms. It also measures leading indicators: Just as there are leading and lagging indicators in the overall balanced performance measurement system, there are drivers and outcomes in the HR value chain as well. It is thus important to monitor the alignment of the HR decisions and systems that drive the HR deliverables. Assessing this alignment provides feedback on HR's progress towards these deliverables and lays the foundation for HR's strategic influence. It lets HR professionals effectively manage their strategic responsibilities and thus encourages flexibility and change.

WHAT IS BALANCED SCORECARD?

A *balanced scorecard* is nothing but an amalgamation of a measurement system, a management system, and a philosophy of management. Company's financial, customer, internal business dynamics, learning and growth are the four key ingredients needed to be never compromised and managed at the strategic levels. This can be done through an HR score card and put into motion through a balance scorecard, an idea put forward by *Kaplan* and *Norton* in the year 1992. Traditional financial reports were retrospective in nature and it does not measure creation or destruction of future economic value, whereas a balanced scorecard used to be prospective in nature focusing customer satisfaction, business process, learning and growth. Customer focus aimed to satisfy, retain and acquire customers in targeted segments. The business process aimed to deliver the value proposition to targeted customers, including innovative products and services, high-quality, flexible, and responsive operating processes, and excellent post-sales support. The organizational learning and growth aimed at developing skilled, motivated employees; providing access to strategic

information, aligning individuals and teams to business unit objectives. (Kaplan, 1999)

The *Balanced Scorecards* were introduced to assess the performance and to embark on a strategy that would see it adopting this approach to broaden the assessment base using a concept familiar to the business. (Ashley, 2004). The initial IT Balanced Scorecard was though developed by *Kaplan & Norton* however, that can be reworked to a more contemporary model and scorecards are now provided periodically across the organizations making it mandatory as a skill to be possessed by HR managers. The balanced scorecard method can be applied to any organization, be it mission driven, profit driven, nonprofit, and governmental organizations. The companies are adopting a Balanced Scorecard to a change, growth, and implement. Companies really needed a Balanced Scorecard to implement a business strategy as only less than ten percent strategies are effectively executed. And business strategy is now the single most important issue and will remain so for the next five years. If companies were to improve the management of their intangible assets, they had to integrate the measurement of intangible assets into their management systems. A balanced scorecard retains financial metrics as the ultimate outcome measures for company success, but supplements these with metrics from three additional perspectives – customer, internal process, and learning and growth – that we proposed as the drivers for creating long-term shareholder value. (Kaplan, 2010). An earlier version of the balanced scorecard could be found in the 1950s, whereby the General Electric corporate staff group conducted a project to develop performance measures for GE's decentralized business units (Lewis, 1955).

The project team recommended that divisional performance be measured by one financial and following nonfinancial metrics.

1. Profitability (measured by residual income)
2. Market share
3. Productivity
4. Product leadership
5. Public responsibility (legal and ethical behavior, and responsibility to stakeholders, including shareholders, vendors, dealers, distributors, and communities)
6. Personnel development
7. Employee attitudes
8. Balance between short-range and long-range objectives

The development of the strategy management system has transformed the *Balanced Scorecard* from being an extended diagnostic system to an interactive system. Bob Simons considered a balance score card having the following characteristics (Simons, 1995 & 1997).

1. Information generated by the system is an important and recurring agenda addressed by the highest levels of management
2. The interactive control system demands frequent and regular attention from operations managers at all levels of the organization.
3. Data generated by the system are interpreted and discussed in face-to-face meetings of superiors, subordinates, and peers.
4. The system is a catalyst for the continual challenge and debated of underlying data, assumptions, and action plans.

The *Balanced Scorecard* can help in creating a strategy-oriented HR system whereby an HR professionals will have strategic and other skills, the HR policies and activities would comprise the HR system itself, and the employee behaviors

and competencies would be the strategic requirements of the company. (Dessler, 2005). Implementation of HR scorecard brings required results if all business leaders continuously keep an eye on all HR processes. Strategy map is proposed in HR level so it takes into consideration only HR processes i.e. HR mission. Learning and Growth, Internal and Customer perspectives are related to the employee's i.e. human capital. The financial perspective shows the final impact from all above mentioned perspectives in the financial area of the organization.

PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT AND BALANCED SCORE CARD (BSC)

The *Balanced Scorecard* has been largely used as strategy and performance framework in private sector organizations throughout the world. After the introduction of New Public Management, it started to be used in public and non-profit organizations in order to facilitate the performance management process. In spite of the increase in the number of studies about its usefulness and uselessness for the private sector, there is still a need to test the feasibility of the BSC as a management framework in the government and non-profit domain. There may be some departments whose operational nature allowed managers to understand the BSC rationale better. Others did not have the same facility for doing so, which resulted in the setting of unachievable objectives, inappropriate targets and hard-to-measure performance indicators. An organization needed to develop a different *Balanced Scorecard* for each business unit rather than create an overall framework for the whole organization. An individual *Balanced Scorecard* for each unit induced cooperation rather than competition and synergy rather than fragmentation. Sponsors are also an important stakeholder in non-profit organizations, and may even be as important as customers are. Moreover, sustainability and institutional support are another important dimension for measuring the performance of nonprofit organizations. (Liddle, 2009).

CONCLUSION

One of the basic requirements of a modern HR Manager has been to develop specific tools and techniques for evaluation of employee and the organization as a whole. Such things are important for managing performance and sustaining the talent in an organization. Developing logical questionnaire related to key performance indicators is the one major step. Data collection and analysis should be scientific and free from any kind of measurement bias. Such efforts would lead to an appropriate HR Score Card and consecutively towards a balanced scorecard.

VITAE

The Author has worked as Divisional Program Manager under the aegis of the *National Rural Health Mission* with the Jharkhand Government. He has remained an ICSSR doctoral and postdoctoral fellows. Taught students at the UG and PG levels subject, such as HR Management and Organizational Behavior.

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